

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE STOCK SIZE OF SMALLHOLDER POULTRY FARMERS IN KWARA STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the factors influencing the stock size of smallholder poultry farmers in Kwara State, Nigeria. Primary data were collected using copies of the questionnaires, while a multi-stage sampling technique was used to select 180 smallholder poultry farmers. Descriptive statistics such as percentages and frequencies were employed to achieve the objectives. The result revealed that most (60%) respondents were male, and the majority (53.33%) were married. About 54.44% of the farmers had post-secondary school education, while only 61.11% of them were members of cooperative societies. The average age of the farmers was 49 years, the mean household size was 7, and the average years of experience in poultry farming was 14 years. The findings further revealed that the mean stock size of poultry farmers was 210. Factors such as the cost of day-old chicken, festive periods, market demands, size of the pen, type of bird to be stocked, the financial capability of the farmer, production type, production season, fear of disease, and availability of labour were among the determinants of the stock size of poultry farmers in the study area. The most used management system by poultry farmers was the deep litter system (47.22%), while the cost of day-old chicken, with a mean value of 3.30, was the most effective determinant of stock size. Based on the findings, the study concludes that many variables influence smallholder poultry farmers' stock size in Kwara State. It was recommended that smallholder poultry farmers should be provided with better access to financial services such as credit, savings, and insurance.

Keywords: Smallholders, Poultry farmers, Stock size

INTRODUCTION

Smallholder poultry farmers play a vital role in global food security and rural livelihoods, contributing significantly to income generation and nutrition. Smallholder poultry farmers typically operate on a small scale with limited resources, often rearing a few birds in backyard systems or small farms (Sonaiya, 2016). These farmers are essential in

meeting local demands for poultry products, particularly in rural and peri-urban areas where large-scale commercial poultry farming is less prevalent (Akintunde, 2015). However, several factors influence the stock size of these smallholder farmers, affecting their ability to expand and sustain their operations. The size of poultry stocks maintained by smallholder farmers varies widely due to various factors. Understanding the factors

that influenced these stock size decisions is crucial for optimizing agricultural practices, improving productivity, and enhancing the well-being of farming households.

The significance of poultry to the national economy is considerable, especially among smallholders who have significantly contributed to the country's economy. In Nigeria, poultry accounts for about 15 percent of the total annual protein intake, with approximately 1.3 kg of poultry products consumed per person each year (Ologbon and Ambali, 2012). The poultry industry has become increasingly important for enhancing employment opportunities and animal food production (Suleiman *et al.*, 2018).

In light of this, this study aims to investigate the factors influencing the stock size of smallholder poultry farmers in Kwara State, Nigeria.

The broad objective of the study is to empirically evaluate the factors influencing the stock size of smallholder poultry farmers in Kwara State.

The specific objectives are to:

- i. describe the socio-economic characteristics of smallholder poultry farmers in the study area.
- ii. identify the management practices adopted by smallholder poultry farmers in the study area.
- iii. determine the average stock size of smallholder poultry farmers in the study area.
- iv. analyse the factors influencing the stock size of smallholder poultry farmers as perceived by the farmers in the study area.
- v. examine the effect of socio-economic variables on stock size of smallholder

poultry farmers

2.0 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study Area

The study was carried out in Kwara State, Nigeria. The state is located in the North Central region of Nigeria and shares boundaries with Niger, Kogi, Osun and Oyo States. It also shares an international border with the Republic of Benin. Kwara State lies in the Guinea Savannah zone, which supports crop farming and livestock rearing. Major occupations include farming, artisanal work, and civil service. The state is home to diverse ethnic groups, including the Yoruba, Nupe, Baruba, and Fulani. This diversity makes Kwara State a significant player in the agricultural and socio-economic landscape of the country (Babalola *et al.*, 2021).

2.2 Sampling Technique

A multistage sampling technique was used to select respondents for the study. In stage 1, three agricultural zones were randomly selected from the state. Stage 2 involved the purposive selection of one block from each of the 3 zones based on their prominence in poultry production. In the third stage, random sampling was used to select 60 respondents per block, making 180 smallholder poultry farmers selected for the study.

2.3 Data Collection and Analysis

Primary data were used for the study, and they were collected using a well-structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was administered to smallholder poultry farmers in the selected communities with the assistance of trained ADP staff who served as enumerators. The objectives of the study were achieved using descriptive

statistics such as percentage, frequency, and mean, as well as multiple regression.

2.4 Model Specification (Multiple Regression)

$$Y = a + b_n X_n + \mu \quad (n = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7)$$

Where:

Y = Stock size

a = Constant term

$b_1 - b_7$ = Regression coefficients to be estimated

X_1 = Age: (measured in years)

X_2 = Gender; (male = 1, female = 0)

X_3 = Education; (total number of years spent in formal education)

X_4 = Marital status, (married = 1, single = 2, widowed = 3, divorced = 4)

X_5 = Household size (measured by the number of people living under one roof)

X_6 = Farming experience (measured in years)

X_7 = Membership of cooperatives (yes = 1, no = 0)

μ = Error term

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Socio-Economic Characteristics of Poultry Farmers in Kwara State

Table 1 shows the socio-economic characteristics of poultry farmers in Kwara State. The results show that 60% of the farmers were male, while 40% were female, corroborating the findings of Oduwaiye *et al.* (2017), who observed a higher male participation in poultry farming compared to females. Additionally, the marital indicates that 53.33% of the farmers were married, 21.78% widowed, 17.11% divorced, and 7.78% single, aligning with the study by Ogunlade and Adebayo (2009), which also reported a predominance of married poultry farmers.

The household size distribution reveals

that 46.22% of respondents had 6-10 household members, 35.56% had 1-5 members, 10.44% had 11-15 members, and 7.78% had more than 16-20 members. The average household size was seven. This aligns with the findings of Ibitoye and Onimisi (2013) Regarding education, the findings show that 54.44% of the farmers had post-secondary education, 30% had secondary education, 10% had primary education, and 5.56% had no formal education. Age distribution data indicate that 43.33% of the farmers were aged 41-50 years, 30% were over 50 years, 17.78% were aged 31-40 years, and 8.89% were aged 30 years or younger. The average age was 49 years, suggesting that most farmers were within a productive age range, capable of actively engaging in farming. This aligns with Adisa *et al.* (2017), who found the average age of poultry farmers to be 42 years.

The respondents' farming experience varied, with 35% having over 30 years of experience, 27.78% having 21-30 years, 23.33% having 11-20 years, and 13.89% having 10 years or less. The average farming experience was 14 years, indicating that experienced farmers likely possess better decision-making skills regarding resource allocation and technology adoption, though experience can also lead to resistance to new practices. Finally, 61.11% of the farmers were members of cooperative societies, while 38.89% were not.

Table 1: Socio-Economic Characteristics of Poultry Farmers in Kwara State

Variable	Freq	%
Gender		
Male	100	60
Female	80	40
Marital status		
Single	25	7.78
Married	120	53.33
Divorced	15	17.11
Widowed	20	21.78
Household size		
1 – 5	20	35.56
6-10	70	46.22
11-15	80	10.44
16-20	10	7.78
<i>Mean</i>	7	
Educational level		
No formal school	10	5.56
Primary school	18	10.00
Secondary school	54	30.00
Post-Secondary	98	54.44
Age		
= 30	16	8.89
31 -40	32	17.78
41 -50	78	43.33
> 50	54	30.00
<i>Mean</i>	49	
Experience		
= 10	25	13.89
11 -20	42	23.33
21 – 30	50	27.78
> 30	63	35.00
<i>Mean</i>	14	
Cooperative Society		
Yes	110	61.11
No	70	38.89

3.2 Poultry Farmers' Management Systems in Kwara State

The result presented in Table 2 shows that 47.22% of poultry farmers used deep litter management systems, while only 13.33% used battery cage systems. The result, however, showed that 39.44% of the farmers used both battery cage and deep litter systems. The high usage of the deep litter system among the farmers may be because it is more cost-effective compared

to other systems, as it requires less frequent cleaning compared to the battery cage system. The system also provides a more natural environment for the birds, allowing them to exhibit natural behaviour such as scratching and dust bathing. This aligns with the study on assessment of the management practices by Ajiboye *et al.* (2019).

Table 2: Poultry Farmers' Management Systems in Kwara State

Management System	Frequency	Percentage
Deep litter system	85	47.22
Battery cage system	24	13.33
Both Deep Litter and Battery cage	71	39.44

3.3 Poultry Farmers' Mean Stock Size in Kwara State

The result showing the mean stock size of poultry farmers in Kwara State indicated that the farmers had a mean stock rate of 210. This is important in assessing the farmers' level of operations. Farmers with

significantly higher stock sizes than the mean can find ways to optimise their production, while those who have less than the average can seek ways to increase their stock size. In their study, Babatunde *et al.* (2012) found that the average stock size of poultry farmers was 405.

Table 3: Distribution of Poultry Farmers' Stocking Size in Kwara State

Mean stock Size	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	
	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
210	171.67	248.52

3.4 Determinants of Stocking Rate in Kwara State

Presented in Figure 1 is the result of the rating of the determinants of stock size in Kwara State. The result revealed that the cost of day-old chicken and money in the farmers' hands with mean values of 3.30 and 3.23, respectively, highly influenced

the stock size of poultry farmers in the state. The high impact of the cost of day-old chicken and money in the farmers' hands-on stocking decisions underscores the importance of financial considerations in poultry farming. Farmers need to have sufficient funds to purchase day-old chicks and cover other costs associated with

poultry production. As indicated by Yusuf *et al.* (2016), in their study on financial analysis of poultry production in Kwara State, the stock capacity of poultry farmers is affected by many factors including the cost of resources, and the financial capacity of the farmers. The study also revealed that money in the farmers' hands and the festive period (3.11) had a similar effect on the stock size of farmers in the state. Also, there was not much difference in the effects

of the festive period, seasons of the year (3.11), and market demand for chicken (2.99). The study further revealed that other occupations of poultry farmers (1.96) had the least effect on the stock size of poultry farmers in the state. Emaikwu *et al.* (2011) in their study reported that high feed and chick cost, unavailability and untimely delivery of farm inputs inadequate capital and poor extension services were factors that affected flock size.

Figure 1: Poultry farmers' rating of the determinants of stock size in Kwara State

3.5 Influence of Socio-Economic Characteristics on the Stock Size of Poultry Farmers

Table 4 shows the result of the multiple linear regression analysis on the effect of socioeconomic characteristics of poultry farmers on their stock size. The value of the R^2 is 0.144 while the f-statistics was 2.668, which was significant at a 1% probability level. The result reveals that gender, farming experience, and educational level were significant socio-economic variables influencing the stock size of poultry farmers in the study area.

Gender was significant and hurt the stock size of the farmers. Due to various socio-economic constraints, women may adopt more risk-averse strategies in farming. Maintaining smaller stock sizes could be a way to manage risks in uncertain conditions. This is in line with the assertions of Gbigbi and E-Okoronkwo (2023) that gender affects the stock size of poultry farmers.

Farming experience was significant and had a positive effect on stock size. This implies that farming experience had a significant and positive relationship with the stock size of poultry farmers in the

study area. A significant but positive relationship between farming experience and the stock size of poultry farmers implies that as farmers gain more experience in poultry farming, their stock size tends to increase. This result is in agreement with Adewale and Ojo (2015) who investigated how varying levels of farming experience influence poultry production.

Education is positive and significant at a 1% level of probability. This suggests that as the level of education of poultry farmers

increases, their stock size also increases. Higher education levels often provide farmers with the knowledge and skills required to manage larger poultry stocks more effectively. This can include understanding optimal feeding practices, disease management, and breeding techniques, all of which can lead to higher stock sizes. This is in line with Adebayo and Adeyemo (2016) which highlights how higher levels of education among farmers correlate with improved agricultural practices and increased stock sizes.

Table 4: Influence of Socio-Economic Characteristics on the Stock Size of Poultry Farmers

Variables	B	Std. Error	t-ratio	level of Sig
Constant	29.208	102.589	.285	.776
Gender	-48.907	22.814	** -2.144	.035
Marriage	-.040	3.506	-.012	.991
household size	1.068	1.661	.643	.522
Age	-.383	3.557	-.108	.914
Year of experience	15.276	8.600	*1.776	.079
Educational status	51.583	16.989	***3.036	.003
R ²	0.144			
F- statistics($p < 0.01$)	2.668			

Dependent variable: Stock size; *significant at 10%, **significant at 5%
***significant at 1% level of probability

CONCLUSION

This study provided valuable insights into the factors influencing the stock size of smallholder poultry farmers in Kwara State, Nigeria. The study highlighted the importance of financial resources, particularly the cost of day-old chicken and money in farmers' hands, as major determinants of stock size. Also, market-

related factors such as festive periods and the size of poultry pens were found to have a high impact on stock size. Farmers who can capitalize on market opportunities during festive periods and have adequate infrastructure for poultry rearing are likely to have larger stock sizes.

Overall, this study's findings have important implications for policymakers,

development practitioners, and stakeholders in the poultry industry. By addressing the key determinants identified in this study, interventions can be designed to support smallholder poultry farmers in increasing their stock sizes, improving their livelihoods, and contributing to the sustainable development of the poultry sector.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Smallholder poultry farmers should have better access to financial services such as credit, savings, and insurance. This can help farmers invest in their farms and increase their stock size.
 - ii. Government agencies, financial institutions, and input dealers should ensure that poultry farmers have timely and affordable access to high-quality inputs, including feed, vaccines, and equipment. This can enhance poultry health and productivity, enabling farmers to increase their stock size.
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